

QUESTIONNAIRE (to be completed together with the child)

1	Date:	
Information about the child:		
2	Name:	
3	Age:	
4	Gender identity:	
5	Does your child have hearing loss?	
6	Does your child have a visual impairment?	
7	Does your child have a motor disability?	
8	Does your child have a pacemaker?	
Legal guardian (vårdnadshavare):		
9	Name 1:	
10	Name 2:	
Questions about musical preferences:		
11	On a scale from 0 to 10, rate how strongly you agree with the following statement (please circle one option): My child is interested in music:	
	0 = strongly disagree	10 = strongly agree
	0 - 1 - 2 - 3 - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 - 10	
12	Does your child play a musical instrument, or sing? (please circle one option)	YES / NO
	If YES: Which instrument(s) does your child play?	

	If NO: Do you think that your child would be interested in learning to play a musical instrument?	YES / NO / I DON'T KNOW
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13	Which challenges have you and your child faced when playing acoustic musical instruments (if any)?	
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14	Have you and your child ever used music technology or other electronic tools to create music (e.g. music apps on a phone, MIDI controllers, synthesizers, electronic musical instruments)?	YES / NO / I DON'T KNOW
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	If YES: Which tools have you used?
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15	Do you feel that there are limitations of existing musical instruments/technology that prevent your child from creating music?	YES / NO / I DON'T KNOW
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	If YES: What are the constraints and how do they limit your child's music making?
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16	What kind of music does your child usually prefer to listen to (please provide examples in terms of genres, artists, etc.)?
	